

Language Learning Under Fire: Budget Cuts, Artificial Intelligence, and the Closure of Foreign Language Departments in U.S. Universities

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Higher education in America rippled with anxiety in summer 2023 when West Virginia University (WVU) announced an end to all foreign language teaching, the cutting of its foreign language department, and the dismissal of faculty from the department. Funds assigned by the state to the university were being negotiated, and the president of the university, E. Gordon Gee, offered a proposal that included elimination of all higher-level foreign language teaching. The state's initial proposal, which would have redirected money toward smaller and rural colleges, would have meant reduced funding for West Virginia's flagship university. Gee criticized the state's plan by calling it a "Robin Hood approach," presumably meaning that money would be taken from the rich (i.e., WVU) and given to the poor (the smaller and rural colleges).

The ethical significance of accusing the state of playing Robin Hood is profound, but the closure of foreign-language programs is not unique to WVU. It is important to note that according to *The Chronicle of Higher Education*, this debate exemplifies "policy issues that are familiar in many states where lawmakers wrestle with the same question: how to fairly and effectively distribute limited tax dollars among institutions with very different missions and needs" (Kelderman, 24 August 2018). Foreign language teaching has been assailed in many universities and under many guises for quite some time now. A major recent contributor to this threat was the economic meltdown during the recession of 2008. *The Chronicle of Higher Education* reports that following the recession, in a period of three years (2013 to 2016), 651 foreign-language programs at colleges and universities in the US shut down, a figure the Modern Languages Association calls "stunning" (Johnson, 22 January 2019). The impact of such challenges to the academy, and particularly to foreign-language teaching, is profound, and reflects changes in the academic community, a shift in the organizing philosophy behind the concept of the university as an institution, and, arguably, the effect of technological enhancements that may profoundly affect the future of foreign-language studies. After surveying the history of foreign language study and bilingual education generally in the United States, this paper examines the effect of the development of a corporate structure on second-language study, and question the efficacy of artificial intelligence as a replacement for foreign-language acquisition.

Second-Language Study in the United States: A Brief History

The study and presence of foreign languages in America has a long history, both as regards their teaching and their use in education in general. In the New England colleges of the 17th century,

teaching was conducted in Latin, and Greek and Hebrew were considered essential to the curriculum (White, 2007, pp. 28-29). These schools' main purpose was to train clergy. Emphasis on the classical languages continued in the Ivy League, however, for more than two centuries, even as the concentrations supported by university education expanded. At Harvard, for instance, Greek only started being phased out in 1886, while by 1898 an enrollee could "avoid either Latin or Greek without penalty" by demonstrating "harder work in other subjects" (Karabel, 2005, p. 44). During these centuries, teaching in languages other than English was common throughout America, especially at lower education levels and in immigrant communities, where English might have been considered the foreign or second language.

Carlos J. Ovando has mapped out a series of phases in the American perception of bilingual education. He describes the attitude toward foreign languages from the 17th through much of the 19th century as "Permissive," since it involved a general tolerance for foreign languages, mostly based on the status of the US (and, before 1776, the British colonies) as a nation of immigrants. Sometimes attempts were made to impose English-language instruction on these groups; Benjamin Franklin, for example, "frustrated by his inability to influence German speakers in Pennsylvania ... urged in 1753 that English schools be established in [German-speaking] communities" (Crawford, 1 April 1987), without much success. At the time of the Continental Congress there were apparently even movements to make German or Hebrew the national language, largely as an expression of the anti-British sentiment generated by the Revolutionary War (Crawford, 1 April 1987, p. 10).

As the nation grew and became more established in the 19th century, English became more dominant. Still, laws were passed to allow teaching in languages other than English in, for example, Ohio (1839), Louisiana (1847), and New Mexico (1848) where teaching in German, French and Spanish respectively was authorized (Crawford, 1 April 1987). No attempt was made to actively promote multilingualism or second-language study, but rather there was a general attitude encouraging "linguistic assimilation without coercion" (Ovando, 2003, p. 4).

In university-level education, study of modern foreign languages did not become common until the late 19th century. This interestingly coincides with the beginning of what Ovando calls the Restrictive period, a time when trends developed to control second-language use and teaching. Ovando claims this phase lasted until the start of the Cold War, and was marked by several "repressive policies" that came into play "for very different reasons" (2003, p. 4). At this time, for example, native languages were actively suppressed. Despite the colonial establishment of native language dictionaries in an effort to convert indigenous peoples to Christianity, in the restrictive period educational institutions such as missionary schools regularly forced native American students off reservation and punished them for speaking their own tongue. The Cherokee, for example, who had the advantage of the syllabary invented by Sequoyah, managed after their forced migration to Oklahoma in 1838 to reach a 90% literacy rate in their tribe. This accomplishment was shattered when, starting in 1879, children were forced into English-only off-reservation schools. According to James Crawford, through this act "the Cherokees were transformed from the most literate to the least literate tribe" (Crawford, 1 April 1987).

The suppression of native American languages was accompanied by reaction against immigrant languages, a symptom of the xenophobia that developed with the arrival of groups other than the

traditional German, Swedish, and other northern Europeans. These new immigrants came from southern and eastern Europe and Asia, and included Jews. For different reasons, reactions against speaking and teaching German started with American involvement in World War One. In other words, language restrictions became markers of “instrumental or symbolic politics” (Crawford, qtd. in Ovando. 2003, p. 6) involving policies aimed at promoting “practical and ideological principles” (Ovando. 2003, p. 6), often to defend power relations and the status quo:

language policy restrictionism and promotion of English became more important as an ideological support for the new imperialism, as a practical instrument of colonial rule, and as a form of social control at home. (Ovando, 2003, p. 18)

Language restriction served nationalist and ethnocentric or antisemitic purposes. Kathleen Stein-Smith explains that “the melting pot metaphor used to describe American Society for much of the 19th and 20th centuries” assumed that “assimilation and integration into the dominant English-speaking culture [should occur] simultaneously” (Stein-Smith 49-50).

The era following World War Two, especially in and after the 1960s, saw the rise of what Ovando calls “The Opportunist period,” a trend that in his view lasted until Reagan’s presidency. This period saw an increased interest in teaching foreign languages in American schools and universities, and paralleled the movement away from American isolationism into global involvement. A key moment in the launching of this trend was the establishment of the Defense Language Institute in Monterey, California, which gave a boost to foreign-language studies nation-wide. According to William L. White, World War Two and its aftermath, including the Cold War, highlighted a “need for functional language users” and “broke the foundations on which languages were taught [prompting] instructors to focus on oral and aural skills rather than verb conjugations and rote vocabulary translations” (White, 2007, p. 32).

Sputnik’s launch in 1957 “shook Federal policies in teaching of foreign languages, mathematics, and science, and led the creation of the National Defense Education Act in 1958. One of the act’s primary goals was to raise the level of foreign language teaching in the United States” (Ovando, 2003, p. 7). Ovando sees this period as “encouraging the study of foreign language for English monolinguals, at great cost and with great inefficiency” (Ovando, 2003, p. 7). Study of foreign languages was also impacted by other events. One factor that profoundly influenced foreign language teaching developed at Coral Way Elementary School in Florida, where well-to-do refugees from the Cuban revolution insisted that their children be educated in both English and Spanish. In this period the increased attention to Civil Rights in the 1960s led Congress to pass the Bilingual Education Act in 1968, meant (not always successfully) to provide federal funding for bilingual education. The Act led, among other things, to the implementation of ESL programs throughout the country.

The election of Ronald Reagan as president, however, saw the beginning of a reaction against bilingual education and foreign language learning. Ovando sees this “Dismissive Period” (Ovando, 2003, p. 12) as continuing to the time of his writing, but recent events suggest that the trend has continued. As he puts it, “The politics of language education during the Reagan and Bush administrations provided the context for the anti-bilingual seeds that were sewn during the 1980s and continued in the 1990s” This period saw the development and strengthening of movements like U.S. English, English Only, and English First (Ovando, 2003, p. 13), and a

generation of “antipathy, especially toward strong forms of bilingual education, [which] is rooted in nativistic and meltingpot ideologies that tend to demonize the ‘other.’ Because bilingual education is much more than a pedagogical tool, it has become a societal irritant involving complex issues of cultural identity, social class status, and language politics” (Ovando, 2003, p. 14).

Regarding bilingual education, Reagan said,

It is absolutely wrong and against American concepts to have a bilingual education program that is now, openly, admittedly dedicated to preserving [the students’] native language and never getting them adequate in English so they can go out into the job market and participate. (Reagan, qtd. in Crawford, 1999, repeated in Ovando, 2003, p. 12)

Enrollment in upper-level foreign language programs in the US showed a fairly regular increase despite Reagan’s criticism, but not one as high as enrollments were in the 1960s (where a ratio of 16.5 students studying languages per 100 students was reached in 1965). The ratios went from a low of 7.3 students enrolled per 100 in 1980 to a peak of 9.1 to 100 in 2006, but then fell back to 1983 levels (7.5 per 100) as the 2008 recession sank in (*L’œuf ou la poule?*). But as the title of a report on these trends suggests, one might ask if it is “*L’œuf ou la poule*” (“The egg or the chicken,” a reversal of the English-language commonplace “Which came first, the chicken or the egg”) that lies behind these plummeting trends. The ‘chicken or the egg’ cliché questions causality; the decline in foreign language enrollment at upper levels might stem from the significant cuts to primary- and secondary-level programs at this time as much as declining interest at the university level impacts primary- and secondary-level foreign language instruction. Early exposure might generate early interest and later facility.

A loss of student interest in language studies might contribute to a lack of training of foreign-language teachers, encouraging the closure of programs, and so leading to a lack of trained foreign language teachers. The trend to eliminate lower-level programs is made clear by Koyfman, who states that “During the 2009-2010 school year, 50.7 percent of higher education institutions in the U.S. required foreign language credits for a baccalaureate, down from 67.5 percent 15 years prior. For high schools, there is no compulsory language requirement in any of the 50 states” (Koyfman). Emily’s Blog states that “American students are falling behind due to the way language is taught” and that “in 2017, only 20% of American students stud[ied] foreign language in K-12 schools,” whereas in Europe the “median percentage of students studying a foreign language [is] 92%” (Jenkins). The downward trend in K-12 foreign language teaching is mirrored by declining interest at the university level. MLA reported in 2010 that “Enrollments in languages other than English at US institutions of higher education ... continued to grow over the past decade and are diversifying to include an increasingly broad range of language studies” (New MLA Survey), but only a few years later reported that “Aggregate enrollments in all languages decreased by 6.7% between 2009 and 2013” (Modern Language Association, Highlights), and that “study of languages other than English at the university level experienced an unprecedented drop of 16.6% between 2016 and 2021,” an issue that spells “trouble for national security” (Cohn). This collapse may mark the apogee of the Reagan revolt against second-language incorporation.

Foreign language teaching in the United States has consistently faced challenges at both the lower and the university levels. According to Stein-Smith, in 2016 only about 10% of the population spoke more than one language, though if immigrants are factored in, this number rises to 25%. For Stein-Smith, this is a problem; the “Foreign Language Deficit,” as she calls it, is prominent in all Anglophone countries, and has led to increasing cultural isolationism, so that, for instance, intervention before the 9/11 attacks on the World Trade Center and the Pentagon might have been possible if US intelligence services had had more interpreters who understood Arabic. The challenge to foreign-language teaching have only increased as the American university has moved towards a corporate model based on profit for shareholders, and more recently by the possibilities offered by machine translation.

The University as Corporation

The president of WVU, E. Gordon Gee, has held administrative positions at several universities and university systems, including a stint as president of Brown University between 1998 and 2000, where faculty and students accused Gee of treating the university “more like a Wall Street corporation than like an ivy league university” (“E. Gordon Gee”). But the treatment of universities as corporations is becoming increasingly prevalent in American society. It both creates and stems from the conundrum that hegemonic institutions have, by their institutional status and by their dominance, the ability to generate higher costs and the need to engage in higher rates of raising institutional finances, either through state support of students or through research grants. Such institutions tend to attract wealthier students, both from in-state and from out-of-state, who are often able to pay the higher tuition rates without significant support. In West Virginia’s case the state’s legislative policy was initially designed to support students from within the state in order to encourage higher in-state graduation rates. In other words, the initial policy seems to have been meant to aid those who are less well off. But the hegemony and status of WVU has led the governor to call on the smaller institutions to “rely on the guidance of the larger institutions” (Kelderman, 2023), which are seen to have greater “expertise” (Kelderman, 2023) in promoting the interests of colleges and universities generally, whether those institutions are small or large, rural or urban. From a certain perspective the executive and legislative branches have thus been seeking an efficient way of continuing services while trying to avoid raising tuition for students.

But one must ask whether efficiency or the university system as a whole is best served by the elimination of programs, and also why second-language teaching has become a bugbear in this wave of efficiency-minded attrition. One might also ask what the real forces are behind these slashes to programs that promote further knowledge of various languages. In the case of WVU, the truth of the matter, according to *The Chronicle of Higher Education*, is that the school was confronting a \$45,000,000 deficit, and part of the fix to this problem was to eliminate 12 undergraduate and 20 graduate programs by dropping the Department of World Languages, Literatures, and Linguistics (Bauman, 2023), along with graduate degrees in Mathematics, upper-level degree programs in Higher Education Administration, and the Art History major (Gutkin, 2023). 169 faculty lines were set to be cut. At the same time president Gee was criticized for amending the language of the code of conduct to include statements that faculty appointment letters require use of phrases such as “accept and encourage change that is for the greater good”

and “avoid conduct that reflects adversely on the image of the University” (Gutkin, 2023). Faculty have also been asked to sign a waiver stating that “all employees are expected to comply with the WVU values and code of conduct”; not signing within ten business days of issuance of the memo was considered a sign of no longer wishing to remain employed at the university (Gutkin, 2023). Linked to this notice was a copy of the code of conduct, including a request that faculty “respect the decisions that have been made in the best interest of the university” (Gutkin, 2023). One could interpret this to mean that any protest against elimination of entire university departments would be a violation of the code of conduct, and grounds for censure or dismissal.

The total number of programs recommended for elimination was 32—12 undergraduate and 20 graduate programs (Bauman, 2023). This cutback related to the predicted \$45,000,000 shortfall estimated for 2024, projected forward to \$75,000,000 in 2028 if no action was taken (Bauman, 2023). Also predicted was a decline over the next few years of high-school students graduating in West Virginia and in the nation as a whole. This shortfall was bolstered by the collapse of enrollment predictions for 2020 (40,000 students predicted, a drop of 7000 enrollees by 2033), no doubt enhanced by the pandemic, but also linked to a strong job market (Bauman, 2023). Still, the leadership repeatedly increased the predicted shortfalls. But other culprits include expenditure on land purchases and construction projects expected to be paid for by enrollments and other sources of funding that never appeared. The shaky budget ride has been going on since the 2008 recession, and has been enhanced by issues with the energy market (affecting presumably the coal industry, which could have a significant effect on West Virginia’s economy) and volatile issues in legislatures that have not always been willing to make appropriations, including those that had been promised. Appropriations dropped 36 percent, or over \$99,000,000, between 2013 and 2022, with adjustments for inflation (Bauman, 2023). The West Virginia Center on Budget and Policy estimates that had the state continued funding at levels like those a decade ago, the shortfall would be approximately \$7,600,000, about 17% of the current deficit (Bauman, 2023).

The University’s budgeting focus has been on expanding research and attracting out-of-state and international students. This has meant expansion via purchase of land and construction. Growth was contingent on attracting students at a time when high-school graduation rates were declining and college attendance wavering. There also was a drop in Saudi and Chinese students starting in 2018, and perhaps reflecting the increased anti-immigrant sentiment and international tension associated with the first Trump presidency. Thus while the university aimed to increase enrollment by 2018, with a goal of 20% enrollment growth in three years, these expectations were linked to acquisition of land for various projects, including a recreational complex, a baseball park and stadium, residential housing, and parking space, and the purchase of residence halls, a library, a gym, and a bookstore from a rival college that closed its doors (Bauman, 2023). (Plans also included purchase or construction of medical/science research centers, a basketball practice field, a greenhouse, an art museum, and buildings for sports science and student health centers, as well as space for the College of Business and Economics, agricultural facilities, and advanced engineering research facilities, as well as student recreational fields and an animal annex [Bauman, 2023].) These impressive schemes were topped by advertising video boards for an arena and asbestos removal funds. All this was going on while the university was paying off loans and debts at a cost of \$35,000,000 annually. Matters were problematized when federal

funding froze in 2011 due to infighting pertaining to budget disputes between Democrats and Republicans, sometimes leading to total government shutdown.

Why is Foreign Language Teaching a Target? AI and Foreign Language Teaching

Financial woes stemming from financial crises exacerbated by politics and poor planning are primary causes of the decisions that led to the cutting of second-language studies at WVU. But one might ask why foreign language teaching so often has been targeted in moments of budgetary crisis? Anti-immigration sentiments, the drop in international student enrollment, and the view that English is the lingua franca of the globalized world may in part account for the cuts to foreign language programs. (The fact that English can be called a *lingua franca* in the present-day globalized market itself speaks to the ultimate ephemerality of hegemony.) But another factor may be the perception that somehow, foreign language acquisition is no longer as pertinent as it once might have been. The development of instant online translation services may be having a profound effect on the perceived need to acquire foreign language skills. Though a majority of Americans have expressed disapproval of the West Virginia program cuts, it is true that increasingly, in the views of some, the need for language acquisition may be being undercut by the accessibility of instant cyber translation.

This is not just an issue related to foreign language acquisition. Increasingly artificial intelligence is developing the ability to write papers for students, sometimes making it difficult to recognize the difference between mediocre student-generated writing and AI-generated work (Emphatic-Mouse). This might also hold true also for second language writing, where student performance is usually even more rudimentary than it is in native or first-language use. A recent study centered on translation from Arabic to English found that “Students who used the Reverso app had fewer Lexical, Cohesion, Omission, and Text-type errors than those who did not use a translation app” (Alotaibi & Salamah, 2023), showing the possibilities digital translation services offer to language learning, teaching, and translation functions. Similar arguments could be made for teaching skills in mathematics and other fields where AI can generate viable content.

While elimination of error is of course a major goal in any teaching environment, the cost to knowledge brought about by AI auto-correction or other features needs to be considered. In mathematics, knowing how to use a slide rule, itself a “technical fix,” is no longer important. This happily dropped skill disappeared when hand calculators, now built into telephones and ubiquitous in the world of numbers, were developed to compute operations. Loss might be noted in the ability of students to do basic calculations, however (Carroll, 2015). In languages similar problems occur with the adoption of AI or machine technology (MT). A study of students learning English as a second language asked the question, “Are MT users influenced by its output in such a way that they change their linguistic behavior in the second language to mirror what they read or hear via the MT?” A syntactic priming experiment was used to see whether Portuguese-speaking participants’ language behavior in English would change after they used the Google Translate app. The sentence ‘the office table was broken’ was used, as this word order does not exist in Portuguese. Portuguese speakers typically say, ‘the table of the office was broken’ (*a mesa do escritório estava quebrada*). However, after seeing that the MT app translated the sentence to the more challenging ‘the office table was broken’, the students

adapted their language behavior to mirror Google Translate's alternative structure when describing images in English. "This experiment shows that exposure to an English syntactic alternative can lead to that same syntactic alternative being reused in subsequent speech, even when it is not the speaker's preferred English syntactic alternative," said Natalia Resende, who conducted the experiment. But she adds as a caveat, "Although this may be correct, they get there without learning the grammatical rules behind the sentence" ("How Machine Translation," 2021). This of course means that the student performs the operation without knowledge of the mechanism controlling the operation, in this case grammatical or usage rules. The skill developed is cutting and pasting the passage to be translated, rather than the grammatical rule itself.

These sorts of issues are compounded when one works with more complex or literary texts, which sometimes involve an intense knowledge of the context, the intended meaning, the idioms, and the allusions made in the text. Consider a translation of a passage from Abdellatif Laâbi's "Mon cher double" ("My Dear Double") which involves allusion to Greek mythology. The passage in French reads,

À moi les montagnes russes
le défilé des Thermopyles
Charybde et Scylla
les écuries d'Augias
le supplice de Tantale
(Laâbi, 2024, p. 81)

In English it could be translated as follows

For me it's the roller coaster
the pass of Thermopylae
Charybdis and Scylla
the Augean stables
the torment of Tantalus
(Laâbi, 2024, p. 80)

In context this passage ostensibly contrasts Laâbi's political involvement with his imagined double's erratic passivity or "coolness." But it also takes us from the famous Greek battle at Thermopylae into Homer's *Odyssey*, then to the labors of Heracles, and finally to Tantalus's condemnation in Tartarus before it verges into contemporary Middle Eastern conflicts, setting up a comparison between the chaos of the mythical world and modern times. This is a topsy-turvy roller coaster ride indeed. But it is introduced by an untranslatable pun: Laâbi's term for "roller coaster" is *montagnes russes*, literally "Russian mountains," possibly making an oblique reference to the Caucasus Mountains, and so possibly alluding to Prometheus's fate for rebelling against Zeus by giving humans fire, i.e., intelligence, and perhaps even life, as in some tellings Prometheus creates humans out of clay (Johnston & Johnston, 2020). Whether or not the allusion to the Russian mountains is meant to echo the origin of human woe in the work of Prometheus, the passage involves an electrifying spin through classical mythology where such an allusion would not be improbable. The reference to *montagnes russes* suggests some of the

difficulties involved in translation, features that would be missed in the literal translation offered by AI systems. It can be problematic when working with idioms such as this one that cannot be translated directly. The situation may be further complicated if the French idiom's syntax has been remolded and fused to reflect the sounds and structures of oral Arabic, as often happens in Laâbi's work. Idioms such as the English "It's raining cats and dogs" have no meaning in other languages unless the literal meaning is changed; in French it might be rendered "il pleut des hallebardes" ("it's raining halberds").

While increased understanding of the nuances of another culture through its language is one benefit of second-language acquisition, there are several others. Research has suggested that learning a second language enhances working memory functions, task switching abilities, and executive control (Konnikova, 2015) (Konnikova [2015] presents arguments supporting these functions, as well as some arguments against them). For persons who speak two or more languages, decision-making in the non-native language may result in less cognitive bias associated with emotive attachment to the primary language (Keysar, Hayakawaka, & An, 2012). As if these gains in mental functioning weren't enough, there is evidence that speaking more than one language inhibits the development of Alzheimer's and other dementia-related diseases, adding apparently more than four years of clear mental functioning when the disease develops (Bialystok, Craik, & Freedman, 2007; Alladi et al., 2013). The benefits thus go beyond the university life and potentially are life-long. As White puts it, "the idea that foreign language study enhances a variety of mental skills, including problem-solving, creativity, and overall cognitive functions remains to this day" (White, 2007, p. 57).

Conclusion

In his 2007 doctoral thesis exploring professorial attitudes toward foreign language studies at WVU, William L. White claimed that

Changes in higher education have arrived with such rapidity that many of the taken-for-granted notions that provided a sense of comfort and place to generations of college and university faculty are not [*sic*] longer valid. The torrent of change has left professors in the decline of enrollment in foreign language and other liberal arts programs alienated from the venture-capital, entrepreneur-minded universities that dot the landscape of the nation. (White, 2007, p. 80)

White's recognition of the alienating factors controlling the increasingly corporate university model currently taking control of the university means that it is often doubtful that "the values articulated by administrators represent those held by professors" (White, 2007, p. 61), much less those held by students, whose "interests" are potentially more directly represented by the university's focus on rec centers, basketball courts, and other amenities meant to attract the customer rather than provide education as they pass through the university system into the working world. Certainly foreign-language studies are not necessarily fun, particularly when required. White points out a 50% drop in student enrollment in foreign-language courses since the 1960s, a trend he attributes to the development of narrow-range professional course lines, continuous poor student performance, and outdated modes of teaching he connects to the focus on literary works as opposed to oral-aural learning.

The sad fact of the matter is, as White points out, that “bottom-line financial accounting has assumed an important and perhaps determining role in the planning and operations of institutions of higher learning” (White, 2007, p. 37). Focus on passing the student through the university into the workforce often assumes the shape of a stream-lined, no nonsense learning of skills and knowledge needed for the profession aimed at, leaving out such ‘unnecessary’ foci as foreign-language study, let alone the arts, literature, and other seemingly non-essential areas of study. The idea of the efficient worker, as opposed to the well-rounded educated citizen, serves well what Robert Mitchell calls the “utilitarian” philosophy of the contemporary school system, where the productive citizen, rather than the realized individual, becomes the end-product (see Mitchell, 2023, pp. 54-59). As White reminds us, “the rise of the professional schools and the prescribed curricula developed by external accrediting agencies is an important force” (White, 2007, p. 78) in contemporary education, and often undercuts the humanistic values that might have been emphasized in the original idea of the university. Coupled with these forces is the sudden emergence of technologies that some say replace the human factor in the economic structure of society, be it robotics replacing factory-line work or self-writing documents generated by AI, or weapons that have the capacity to choose their own targets without human intervention, like those that have been introduced in the conflict between Ukraine and Russia, or the armed flying drones that have been introduced by the Israelis in Gaza. Another AI manifestation is the instant translation function of Google Translate and other programs. The development of these technologies perhaps explains why language departments are increasingly moving toward providing certificates in interpretation as opposed to straight-forward translation as their offering.

President Gee rescinded a bit on his position at WVU, retaining course work in Spanish and Chinese. These changes came after a letter circulated in academia, seeking signatures of support against the position taken by the university, and arguing that the “planned cuts [would] impoverish the intellectual and social culture at WVU” and “permanently damage the reputation of the institution.” The letter argued further that statements issued by president Gee and Provost Maryanne Reed “paint the closure as inevitable because of the underperformance of faculty and programs affected by the cuts instead of acknowledging the ongoing administrative mismanagement of university priorities” (McElhinny, 2023). Whether this plea is heard, one thing is obvious: study of secondary languages remains a targeted area in American academia, and liberal studies and the arts in general, including the language arts, will be targeted as long as universities are seen as corporate entities focused on turning out the next generation of cookie-cut professionals rather than being institutions of learning. As White puts it, “The torrent of change has left professors in the decline of enrollment in foreign language and other liberal arts programs alienated from the venture-capital, entrepreneur-minded universities that dot the landscape of the nation” (White, 2007, p. 80).

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